

On the Italo-French reception of the Book of Abramelin and the three-book recension

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Abstract

It is by now widely known that when Watkins published Samuel Mathers's translation of the Book of Abramelin in 1897, the English-speaking esoteric community became familiarised with a version of the text which was to some degree corrupt and which differed significantly from the form in which it originally circulated in German. The story of this version of the text is nevertheless worth telling, as it is indicative of a rich reception history which is less obviously attested in the German tradition. The three-book recension is originally attested in Italian and its core elements were certainly already present by 1650, not long after the composition in German of the text in its canonical form. It nevertheless represents an abridgement from a much more faithful translation into Italian which did contain all four books. In terra italiana, the text underwent two significant transformations: the first being the abridgement and the introduction of the curious device of the child called upon initially to witness the presence of the Angel, and the second an extensive series of apologetic and Christianizing insertions which clearly suggest a structured process of transmission very akin to that which seems to have characterized the Sworn Book of Honorius. Both of these

transformations seem to have taken place in parts of Italy which were under Spanish influence, possibly the Duchy of Milan in the first instance, but almost certainly Naples or southern Italy in the second. It is from this latter form of the text that the French translation attested in the Arsenal derives.

Introduction

Notwithstanding its foundational significance within Western esotericism, scholarly research into the so-called *Book of Abramelin* has been very limited to date. The *Abramelin*, in its canonical form acquired by the time of the earliest known 1608 Wolfenbüttel manuscript (W1)¹, recounts the story of a Jew from the Palatinate who travels to Egypt in search of magical wisdom. There he is introduced to a procedure whereby a diligent practitioner can acquire a personal relationship with his Guardian Angel which equips him with magical power and the means of its ethical deployment in the world. The Book claims (in what is an evident literary trope) to preserve these instructions to the benefit of the author's younger son, Lamech. The *dénouement* of the Operation is accompanied by a binding of demonic potentates in the service of the newly minted Magician, characteristic of the medieval European grimoire tradition. The four-part manuscript also conserves a book of charms, presented as applicable even in the absence of the Operation, and a section on magic squares, which presupposes success in it.

¹ Herzog August Bibliothek, Wolfenbüttel, *Cod. Guelf.* 47.13 Aug. 4o

The text as we have it shows dependence on a German *Urschrift* no earlier than 1595, as Rick-Arne Kollatsch has shown², although I have argued elsewhere that a thematic analysis requires us to posit earlier sources in some form³. Although the later manuscript witnesses only contribute to a limited extent to establishing the *Urschrift*, the reception history is nevertheless interesting from a number of points of view. As we now know, when Watkins published Samuel Mathers's translation, based on a French text in the possession of the *Bibliothèque de l' Arsenal* in Paris (which we will refer to as Pa1)⁴, the English-speaking esoteric community became familiarised with a version of the text which was to some degree corrupt and which differed significantly from the form in which it originally circulated in German. Importantly, it also contained extensive insertions which testify to its use in some sort of initiatory or at least tightly controlled context.

The origins of the three-book recension

Perhaps for reasons of a lack of linguistic familiarity, very few people seem to be aware that the three-book recension is originally attested in Italian and its core elements were certainly already present by 1650, not long after the composition in German of the text in its canonical form. Despite its many curious innovations, which we shall summarize below, and which ultimately resulted in a very different form of the text, this manuscript tradition bears witness in a number of respects to an older recension than is attested in the “Saxon lineage” which came to dominate the German-speaking world. This shows that the canonical text had a

² Kollatsch, Rick-Arne (ed., 2021), *Des Abraham von Worms Buch der wahren Praktik von der alten Magie: Ein als jüdisch fingierter Magietext des frühen 17. Jahrhunderts*.

³ Dionysos, Frater (2025), “On the Origins of the Abramelin Operation in Islamic Magic” Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15340376

⁴ Ms. 2351, available online at <https://archivesetmanuscrits.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cc830818>

Nachleben of its own in Italy, and later in France (and later than that, within the English-speaking occult community), albeit ultimately in a much altered form.

The Brescia manuscript and the *Urübersetzung*

Surprisingly, and as no one seems to have noticed, the canonical four-book text was initially translated into Italian in a form which seems to have been remarkably faithful to the original.

We would know nothing of the existence of this translation, nor even suspect it, were it not for a late and somewhat haphazard copy of it conserved in the Bibliotheca Quiriniana in Brescia (Br)⁵. The existence of this manuscript was first noted by Maria Elena Loda⁶, but its position within the manuscript tradition was not further discussed. Having examined it, I can confirm that close linguistic correspondences make it certain that the remaining known Italian manuscripts, and all of the French ones (except the Basel manuscript, which is an independent translation from German, and parts of the Rouen manuscript⁷), derive from this original translation. It is free from the hallmark signatures of the Saxon lineage of the text, and correspondingly closer to W1.

⁵ Blindata Ms.I.V.13

⁶ Loda, Maria Elena (2015), “Libri, Maghi e Misteri”, *MedioEvo*, Jan. 2015

⁷ Ms. 3474, Desbois-1, Villon Library, Rouen. The latter, although based on Pa1, has also drawn from a German source in the Saxon lineage in order to supplement it with a translation of the book of charms (the canonical book two) and to complete the squares (which it seems to have wanted to do, although only the first six appear in the manuscript).

The Vienna manuscript

How the manuscript Wi1 ended up in Vienna⁸ we do not know for certain, but an article by Monika Franz appears to link it to the extensive collection of Philipp Eduard Fugger, which was sold to the Hapsburg imperial library in 1655. Fugger was an Italian speaker and spent extensive time in the country, making it plausible that the document would have appealed to him, though as he died in 1618 we cannot be confident that the acquisition was not rather carried out by a son or grandson. In any case, either date demonstrates an early transmission of the text from Germany to Italy⁹. An early inscription in Latin on the manuscript says that it was originally composed in German, but draws this conclusion from internal evidence and specifically the end of I.4. A later annotation observes, presumably disapprovingly, that the book is “magical or goetic”¹⁰.

Wi1 is written in a careful hand, but in an Italian which is at times so poor that we can be confident that the scribe was not a native speaker. It is evident enough on internal grounds that it contains a number of corruptions and lacunae, and a comparison with Br, and even with the later manuscripts V, Pm and Pa1, confirms this. It therefore clearly copied an earlier Italian manuscript which was the locus for the key developments to which it bears witness and which was also the ultimate source of V and Pm. We refer to this source text as RQ.

⁸ Austrian National Library Ms. 10579, available online at <https://onb.digital/result/1000738D>.

⁹ In the catalogue it is given a date of around 1600 but this is hardly likely.

¹⁰ The library has a second manuscript, in German, which originally came from the personal collection of Peter Lambeck, who became Court librarian in 1683, referred to as Wi2 (Ms. 10580, available online at <https://onb.digital/result/117C47E6>). This manuscript is derived from the Saxon lineage.

Wi1 contains certain hispanicisms, absent from Br but conserved in V and Pm, which seem to require the origin of RQ to have been in a setting influenced by Spanish usage. The Duchy of Milan is a plausible candidate.

The Venice and Parma manuscripts

A further manuscript in Italian, from the Correr library in Venice, was published by Gaspare Licandro in 2015¹¹. This manuscript (which we will refer to as V) clearly derives from an exemplar close to, but earlier than, Wi1. At the same time, it innovates in significant respects, and follows very closely the text from which the *Arsénał* manuscript must have been translated. It cannot, however, be identical with this text since it lacks the first six chapters of book one, clearly viewed as inessential by the copyist for the purposes to which he envisaged putting it¹².

It was made use of, supposedly, by “*the great A: M: et F: P: M:sis*” and is said to have been copied from “the original” which was to be found in the library of the Holy Roman Emperor Frederick III. Frederick reigned from 1452 to 1493 and this is therefore impossible; it is

¹¹ Licandro, Gaspare (2015), *La Sacra Scienza di Abrahamelin: Un manoscritt settecentesco di magia angelica a Venezia*, Rome: Tipheret. The manuscript in question is MS Correr 498. I have only consulted Licandro’s transcription so cannot guarantee its accuracy.

¹² Within the German tradition, there is some evidence suggesting circulation of a “taster” edition of the text containing only book one. It is therefore also possible that V may have been a text given to adepts whose initial study of that “taster” edition was deemed satisfactory; it certainly calls for the greatest foresight in transmission of the text, so such a strategy would be entirely consistent.

probably a supposition based on the traditional dating of the “translation from the Hebrew” (which certainly never happened either¹³).

We may speculate that the abbreviation perhaps stood for “*Adeptus Maior* (or *Arcanorum Magister*) *et Filius Philosophorum Messinensis*”, typical esoteric honorifics. Messina was a noted center of occult philosophy in the Middle Ages as it was a crossroads between Arabic, Jewish and European culture, though this was no longer the case by the mid-17th century.

The manuscript itself is datable to the 18th century according to Licandro, but he does not explain his reasoning. It was in the possession of Teodoro Correr (1750-1830). It claims to have been copied (and Pm agrees with this detail) in “*anno mundi* 3462”, which would mean, according to Licandro, 486 BCE, and according to the Jewish reckoning 299 BCE; either date is obviously impossible. A scribal error for “5462” is possible, which would bring it closer to the internal dating of the text, or even to an actually plausible date on the latter, Jewish assumption.

The redactor is evidently a Christian deeply (though perhaps unwillingly) influenced by Counter-Reformation Catholicism. The text reflects all of the key innovations witnessed to by W11 as we outline them below. However, it also innovates in numerous respects. Although it makes plenty of errors, it is also more conservative than W11 in some respects, conserving for example *Thirama* (as *Tirana*), *Alluph* and *Neschamah* (as *Nescamaij*) in the list of spirit

¹³ It is not impossible that some part of what would become the canonical book did exist in Judeo-German, which would certainly have been the case if its author was indeed Jewish, and doubly so if he was concerned to obscure the text. If so, a later transliteration of these parts into Latin script might have been thought of or misunderstood as being a “translation from Hebrew”. However, the typically fantastic nature of such inscriptions certainly does not require us to posit that this was the case.

names, forms lost in Wi1, which seems to skip a line. A significant difference between the two manuscripts is also that V occasionally conserves *segreto* (“secret”) as translation of *geheimnusz* (modern *Geheimnis*), which is always substituted by *misterio* (“mystery”)¹⁴ in Wi1 (in V, *geheimnusz* is usually substituted by *Cabala*). This is further evidence for the stage of the text represented by RQ.

The Parma manuscript Pm¹⁵, which I am here describing for the first time, is closely related to V, down to the omission of the first six chapters, though it has abbreviated it in several places, including leaving out fully half of the final book of squares.

The *Arséna*l manuscript Pa1 is self-evidently a translation of a manuscript in this tradition, which we will call RQ2. It cannot directly depend on either V or Pm since, unlike them, it contains the first six chapters of book one. It is, however, very plausible that its possessor, the French diplomat Count Antoine René de Voyer d’Argenson, did in fact either encounter or, more likely, commission this translation in Venice, where he was stationed and with which he had family ties.

Distinctive features of Wi1

The following are the major ways in which Wi1, and RQ, innovate compared to W1 and Br:

¹⁴ In 17th-century Italian, "*misterio*" had a broader range of meanings than it typically does today, and could refer to mystical doctrine, mystical experience, or secret spiritual knowledge, in addition to its more general meaning of something hidden or inexplicable.

¹⁵ Biblioteca Palatina Parmense, Ms. Parm. 00632

- Book two is eliminated, as are all references to it. Book four is renumbered as book three, and all references to it elsewhere in the book are replaced with the new numbering.
- The Operation is shortened to six months, divided into three periods of two lunar cycles each.
- The addition of a young male child as an agent to facilitate the angelophany.
- A certain blinding of the squares which appears deliberate (in addition to a number of errors of transcription which do not: the squares themselves undergo in many cases reordering and reattributions, that is, their intended use is “shuffled” even when the square itself is transcribed correctly¹⁶).

There is in fact a smoking gun, since the conclusion of book three is entitled *epilogo della terza parte cioè di questi tre libri* (“epilogue to the third part, that is, of these three books”) despite the fact that in the abridgement it is now placed at the end of what has become only the second book.

The loss of book two is easy to account for. It was of limited utility and in any case quite secondary to the purpose of the Book as a whole, with which it is not very integrated. This is in contrast to the squares, which are fully integrated into the Operation in the text of the Book as we have it from W1, such that the purpose of the Operation in part “is” to bind the spirits to carry out the instructions embedded within the squares. Moreover, mining Luther’s 1545 German translation for Biblical charms is widely attested in the German-speaking lands, whereas there was no parallel tradition in Italy.

¹⁶ Thus for example the eleven squares of IV.1 are reordered in W11 relative to W1 as follows: 4,3,1,2,6,9,5,10,11,7,8. This reordering lies at the base of the rest of the tradition, although there are further changes. It is hard to imagine this being the result purely of a scribal error.

The addition of the child is more curious, and was notably questioned by Mathers. Ostensibly, the text states that this element has been added because very many people had been unsuccessful in the Operation without it. If taken at face value, this would obviously suggest a certain tradition of practical use. The background to this seems to be, however, more of a doctrinal nature. Like the *Sworn Book of Honorius*¹⁷, the *Abramelin* offers the adept access to an experience which might have sounded like the Beatific Vision, which is the vision of God accorded to the saints upon their death, but not before, according to the teaching of the Papal encyclical *Benedictus Deus* (1336). Although experiences of angels are not ruled out for believers, and guardian angels were generally thought to belong to the lower choirs precisely because of their interaction with humans, the idea that this was a comparatively simple matter which could be attained through formulaic means rather than extraordinary sainthood would certainly have been suspect. It would have been generally more acceptable to imagine that young children had easier access to such experiences. Wil says that the reason for the difficulty is that the angels one is trying to contact are *di natura straphironea*, a phrase which gets further obscured in the subsequent manuscript tradition. It seems likely that this is somehow a corruption of *seraphica*, that is, that they belong to the class of the Seraphim. The use of young children in the context of scrying was of course attested from antiquity for precisely this reason, and was also employed by John Dee prior to his partnership with Edward Kelley.

¹⁷ Peterson, Joseph H. (2016, ed.), *The Sworn Book of Honorius*, Ibis Press

The adept is able eventually to gain unmediated access to the Angel (and indeed it is not absolutely excluded that he could also do so without recourse to this device), but only once the latter has communicated a special sign, similar to those of the final book.

This latter idea seems to draw directly on Iamblichus, *De Mysteriis*, IX.9, where he states that “when the personal daemon comes to be with each person, then he reveals the mode of worship proper to him and his name, and imparts the particular manner in which he should be summoned”¹⁸. More curious, however, are the two squares which the adept and the child are supposed to wear on their forehead in order to bring about this outcome. In RQ2, these signs are based on the thematic words *URIEL* and *ADAM*, and consist of numbers which constitute a substitution cipher, the key to which is the Vulgate text of Psalm 6. Uriel’s name means “Light of God” and in 2 Esdras 4:2 his role is to mediate divine knowledge due to the inability of man in his fallen state to grasp it. This is doubtless the tradition being referred to here. In W11, however, the two signs are much more obscure. They may similarly be a substitution cipher and they have the same form (5x5 and 4x4), and so the later tradition is clearly also present here in embryo: but they certainly do not encode the same letters and words.

¹⁸ Clarke, Emma et al. (2003, eds.), *Iamblichus: De Mysteriis*, Atlanta: Society of Biblical Literature, p. 341. Ficino’s Latin translation was published in 1497.

As for the abbreviation of the time frame, are we to assume this was simply a practical matter? It is hard to say, but the adaptation is not a simple scaling. In the canonical text, at III.12, a procedure of sanctification is foreseen. The intention seems to be, as I read it, that this is a one-off ritual with which to begin the third semester, though it is possible that it is intended to supplement the instructions in III.9 and be performed throughout this final period. In either case, W11 distorts the logic, since the consecration becomes a prelude to the final period of angelic and spirit invocations, extending it from six to seven days, as a result of which the final and climactic adjuration, during which the spirits are required to swear on the squares, now takes place on the Sabbath, an arrangement so evidently implausible, and explicitly ruled out in III.20, that one wonders how it was not noticed.

Further innovations in RQ2

As mentioned, V and Pm lack the first six chapters, but because they are so close to Pa1 it is reasonable to rely on the latter for the likely content of the missing six chapters of RQ2 as well. The main innovations in this text are the following:

- Extensive redactions testifying to the use of the book in an initiatory or at least highly secretive context and the need for extreme prudence in passing it on. This goes so far as even to remodel the transmission of the Sacred Magic by Abramelin in I.4 along the lines which are subsequently prescribed. In my view it is probable that the *Sworn Book* is exercising here some influence.
- A fair amount of deliberate antisemitic rhetoric

- A great deal of accommodation to Catholic church teaching

The precautions which the possessor of the Magic is called upon to observe in its further transmission are such as, whether coincidentally or not, to extend in practice the period of the Operation once again to eighteen months, because the candidate must be observed for at least six months and must also spend six months in study of the text before commencing.

In the interpolated and appended sections, V and Pm are written in an Italian which is marked by southern stylistic features and it seems that RQ2 may have originated in Naples or elsewhere in southern Italy. Although they are likely too early to have influenced it directly, figures like Giambattista della Porta (1535–1615) and Tommaso Campanella (1568–1639) represent something of the heterodox possibilities alive in the city during this period. The Basilian Greek monasteries, where the practice of hesychasm continued to an extent in southern Italy after the fall of Constantinople, may also represent an element in the milieu favorable to this development.

Typical themes from Aquinas characterize these insertions, including the *gratia praecepti* (the grace given by God to live according to His commandments), *Deus non cogit ad impossibilia* or *Deus impossibilia non iubet* (God does not demand the impossible), the punishment visited by God on the Devil and the fallen angels, and the power given by God to command evil spirits in the name of Christ. Much of this, we may assume, must have constituted a defensive adaptation to the environment in which the practice was exercised and an attempt to preempt, or at least mitigate, obvious ecclesiastical objections. RQ2 also specifically cites the prohibition on the reading of the Bible in the vernacular which followed from the Council of

Trent (though Pa1 omits this, it having presumably by that time become no longer relevant, not to mention being a rather obvious insertion).

The antisemitic rhetoric, of course, also aligned closely with both attitudes in Catholic lands and the formal teaching of the Church, laid out for instance in the (outrageous, let it be said) papal bull *Caeca et Obdurata Hebraeorum perfidia* of 1593. Here also, nevertheless, it may be that adepts were well advised to err on the side of caution by including such sentiments, contemptible as they may be to modern ears, when intending to follow a ritual so closely aligned to the Hebrew scriptures.

It is possible that throughout this reception history in Italy, regarding which it seems likely that further discoveries remain to be made, the *Abramelin* and the *Sworn Book* competed at some level for the attention of adepts seeking to perform the Supreme Ritual. Although they represent somewhat different models, the fact that the central ritual of the latter was significantly shorter (40 days in the southern recension and 72 in the northern) may perhaps have made an eighteen month Abramelin ritual a non-starter. In any case, what is certain is that major efforts and a very high degree of motivation were required in either case to come into possession of the necessary material, such that in reality the work must be viewed as one of sustained commitment during years if not decades.

Conclusion

The Italian reception of the Abramelin represents a fascinating glimpse into the underground circulation of this most demanding of magical texts and the societal conditions which shaped

its development. Both the French reception of the text and the Mathers translation were indelibly marked by this formative milieu even if they were quite unaware of it. In hindsight, it seems a little strange that anyone doubted, knowing the text only in this form, that it emerged from a Catholic environment: it requires a great deal of avoidance of cognitive dissonance to conclude the contrary. At the same time, this reception history gives us an insight into the kinds of process which may have shaped the compilation of the canonical German version as well, regarding which we can unfortunately presently only rely on internal evidence. Whilst in any version it presents many interpretative challenges, it is clear that it was a living text embedded within some sort of community of practice, at least in certain periods. The effort needed to seek out copies and to actually copy it, and the risk which enquiring after it or possessing it entailed, bear witness to evidently quite extraordinary levels of motivation to do the work which it proposed, itself, no doubt, if not a guarantee of success then at least a *conditio sine qua non*.